
LOCALIZED BOUNDED BELOW APPROXIMATE SCHAUDER FRAMES ARE FINITE UNIONS OF APPROXIMATE RIESZ SEQUENCES

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Date: January 1, 2023

Abstract: Based on the truth of Feichtinger conjecture by Marcus, Spielman and Srivastava [*Ann. of Math. (2)*, 2015] and from the localized version by Gröchenig [*Adv. Comput. Math.*, 2003], we introduce the notion of localization of approximate Schauder frames (ASFs) and approximate Riesz sequences (ARSs). We show that localized bounded below ASFs are finite unions of ARSs.

Keywords: Feichtinger conjecture, Frame, Riesz sequence, Localization.

Mathematics Subject Classification (2020): 42C15, 46A45, 46B45.

1. INTRODUCTION

In the beginning years of 21th century, Prof. Feichtinger formulated the following conjecture based on his extensive work on Gabor/Weyl-Heisenberg frames (see [13] for the history and [4, 14, 16–19, 22, 25–28, 36] for general theory).

Conjecture 1.1. [8] (*Feichtinger Conjecture/Marcus-Spielman-Srivastava Theorem*) *Let $\{\tau_n\}_n$ be a frame for a Hilbert space \mathcal{H} such that*

$$0 < \inf_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \|\tau_n\|.$$

Then $\{\tau_n\}_n$ can be partitioned into a finite union of Riesz sequences for \mathcal{H} .

First breakthrough which supported Conjecture 1.1 occurred when Gröchenig proved it for intrinsically localized frames [23]. Shortly afterwards, it has been verified for certain classes of ℓ^1 -self-localized frames, wavelet frames, Gabor frames, frames of translates, frames formed by reproducing kernels and exponential frames/frames of exponentials [2, 3, 6, 29, 30, 35, 39]. Conjecture 1.1 received great attention after establishing its equivalence with Kadison-Singer conjecture [9, 10, 12]. Finally, the Feichtinger conjecture has been solved fully by resolving Weaver’s conjecture by Marcus, Spielman, and Srivastava in 2013 [5, 33, 34, 37, 38]. In this paper, we formulate a Banach space version of Conjecture 1.1 and prove it for bounded below intrinsically localized ASFs (Theorem 2.7).

2. LOCALIZED BOUNDED BELOW ASFs ARE FINITE UNIONS OF ARSs

We consider the following most general notion of approximate Schauder frames. In the entire paper, \mathcal{X} is a separable Banach space and \mathcal{X}^* is its dual.

Definition 2.1. [7, 11, 21] *Let $\{\tau_n\}_n$ be a collection in \mathcal{X} and $\{f_n\}_n$ be a collection in \mathcal{X}^* . The pair $(\{f_n\}_n, \{\tau_n\}_n)$ is said to be an **approximate Schauder frame** (we write ASF) for \mathcal{X} if the **frame***

operator

$$S_{f,\tau} : \mathcal{X} \ni x \mapsto S_{f,\tau}x := \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n(x)\tau_n \in \mathcal{X}$$

is a well-defined bounded linear invertible operator.

We use the following notion of 'bounded below' for ASFs.

Definition 2.2. An ASF $(\{f_n\}_n, \{\tau_n\}_n)$ for \mathcal{X} is said to be **bounded below** if

$$\inf_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |f_n(\tau_n)| > 0.$$

Motivated from the definition of localization of frames [20, 24], we introduce the following notion.

Definition 2.3. An ASF $(\{f_n\}_n, \{\tau_n\}_n)$ for \mathcal{X} is said to be **intrinsically/self localized** if there exist $s > 1$ and $A > 0$ such that

$$|f_n(\tau_m)| \leq \frac{A}{(1 + |n - m|)^s}, \quad \forall n, m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Two notions of Riesz sequences for Banach spaces exist in literature, see [1, 15] and [32]. Here we define another.

Definition 2.4. An ASF $(\{f_n\}_n, \{\tau_n\}_n)$ for \mathcal{X} is said to be an **approximate Riesz sequence** (we write ARS) if there exists a finite partition Q_1, \dots, Q_N of \mathbb{N} such that

$$\mathbb{N} = \bigcup_{j=1}^N Q_j$$

and for each $1 \leq j \leq N$,

$$\inf_{n \in Q_j} \left(|f_n(\tau_n)| - \sum_{m \in Q_j, m \neq n} |f_n(\tau_m)| \right) > 0.$$

Note that for Hilbert spaces, if $\{f_n\}_n$ is determined by $\{\tau_n\}_n$ (Riesz representation), then Definition 2.4 is equivalent (due to positivity) to the definition of Riesz sequence (see [23]). We now formulate the following conjecture (some other are formulated in [31]).

Conjecture 2.5. *Every bounded below ASF can be partitioned as a finite union of ARBs.*

We now prove Conjecture 2.5 for intrinsically localized ASFs with the help of following result.

Theorem 2.6. [23]

(i) For every $s > 1$,

$$D_s := \sup_{x \in \mathbb{R}} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1 + |n - x|)^s} < \infty.$$

(ii) For every $s > 1$, there exists a $C_s > 0$ (which does not depend on δ) such that

$$\sup_{m \in \mathbb{N}} \sum_{n \in \mathbb{N}, n \neq m} \frac{1}{(1 + |n - m|)^s} \leq \frac{C_s}{\delta^s},$$

whenever

$$\inf_{n, m \in \mathbb{N}, n \neq m} |n - m| \geq \delta.$$

LOCALIZED BOUNDED BELOW APPROXIMATE SCHAUDER FRAMES ARE FINITE UNIONS OF APPROXIMATE RIESZ SEQUENCES

Theorem 2.7. *Conjecture 2.5 holds for intrinsically localized bounded below ASFs.*

Proof. Our proof is highly motivated from [23]. Let $(\{f_n\}_n, \{\tau_n\}_n)$ be an intrinsically localized bounded below ASF for \mathcal{X} . Define

$$C := \inf_{n \in \mathbb{N}} |f_n(\tau_n)| > 0.$$

Since $(\{f_n\}_n, \{\tau_n\}_n)$ intrinsically localized there exist $s > 1$ and $A > 0$ such that

$$|f_n(\tau_m)| \leq \frac{A}{(1 + |n - m|)^s}, \quad \forall n, m \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Let C_s be the constant as in Theorem 2.6. Choose natural number M such that

$$\frac{AC_s}{M^s} \leq \frac{C}{2}.$$

We now partition \mathbb{N} into Q_1, \dots, Q_N such that

$$\mathbb{N} := \bigcup_{j=1}^N Q_j$$

and for each $1 \leq j \leq N$,

$$\inf_{n, m \in Q_j, n \neq m} |n - m| \geq M.$$

(Note that there are infinitely many partitions of \mathbb{N} of this type.) Let $1 \leq j \leq N$. Then using (ii) in Theorem 2.6

$$\sup_{n \in Q_j} \sum_{m \in Q_j, m \neq n} |f_n(\tau_m)| \leq A \sup_{n \in Q_j} \sum_{m \in Q_j, m \neq n} \frac{1}{(1 + |n - m|)^s} \leq A \frac{C_s}{M^s} \leq \frac{C}{2}.$$

Therefore for each fixed $1 \leq j \leq N$

$$\begin{aligned} \inf_{n \in Q_j} \left(|f_n(\tau_n)| - \sum_{m \in Q_j, m \neq n} |f_n(\tau_m)| \right) &= \inf_{n \in Q_j} |f_n(\tau_n)| - \sup_{n \in Q_j} \sum_{m \in Q_j, m \neq n} |f_n(\tau_m)| \\ &\geq C - \frac{C}{2} = \frac{C}{2} > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Since j was arbitrary, we get the theorem. □

REFERENCES

- [1] Akram Aldroubi, Qiyu Sun, and Wai-Shing Tang. p -frames and shift invariant subspaces of L^p . *J. Fourier Anal. Appl.*, 7(1):1–21, 2001.
- [2] Radu Balan, Peter G. Casazza, Christopher Heil, and Zeph Landau. Density, overcompleteness, and localization of frames. I. Theory. *J. Fourier Anal. Appl.*, 12(2):105–143, 2006.
- [3] Anton Baranov and Konstantin Dyakonov. The Feichtinger conjecture for reproducing kernels in model subspaces. *J. Geom. Anal.*, 21(2):276–287, 2011.
- [4] John J. Benedetto and David F. Walnut. Gabor frames for L^2 and related spaces. In *Wavelets: mathematics and applications*, Stud. Adv. Math., pages 97–162. CRC, Boca Raton, FL, 1994.
- [5] Marcin Bownik. The Kadison-Singer problem. In *Frames and harmonic analysis*, volume 706 of *Contemp. Math.*, pages 63–92. Amer. Math. Soc., [Providence], RI, 2018.
- [6] Marcin Bownik and Darrin Speegle. The Feichtinger conjecture for wavelet frames, Gabor frames and frames of translates. *Canad. J. Math.*, 58(6):1121–1143, 2006.
- [7] P. G. Casazza, S. J. Dilworth, E. Odell, Th. Schlumprecht, and A. Zsák. Coefficient quantization for frames in Banach spaces. *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, 348(1):66–86, 2008.

- [8] Peter G. Casazza, Ole Christensen, Alexander M. Lindner, and Roman Vershynin. Frames and the Feichtinger conjecture. *Proc. Amer. Math. Soc.*, 133(4):1025–1033, 2005.
- [9] Peter G. Casazza and Dan Edidin. Equivalents of the Kadison-Singer problem. In *Function spaces*, volume 435 of *Contemp. Math.*, pages 123–142. Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, 2007.
- [10] Peter G. Casazza, Matthew Fickus, Janet C. Tremain, and Eric Weber. The Kadison-Singer problem in mathematics and engineering: a detailed account. In *Operator theory, operator algebras, and applications*, volume 414 of *Contemp. Math.*, pages 299–355. Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, 2006.
- [11] Peter G. Casazza, Deguang Han, and David R. Larson. Frames for Banach spaces. In *The functional and harmonic analysis of wavelets and frames (San Antonio, TX, 1999)*, volume 247 of *Contemp. Math.*, pages 149–182. Amer. Math. Soc., Providence, RI, 1999.
- [12] Peter G. Casazza, Gitta Kutyniok, Darrin Speegle, and Janet C. Tremain. A decomposition theorem for frames and the Feichtinger conjecture. *Proc. Amer. Math. Soc.*, 136(6):2043–2053, 2008.
- [13] Ole Christensen. Six (seven) problems in frame theory. In *New perspectives on approximation and sampling theory*, Appl. Numer. Harmon. Anal., pages 337–358. Birkhäuser/Springer, Cham, 2014.
- [14] Ole Christensen. *An introduction to frames and Riesz bases*. Applied and Numerical Harmonic Analysis. Birkhäuser/Springer, second edition, 2016.
- [15] Ole Christensen and Diana T. Stoeva. p -frames in separable Banach spaces. *Adv. Comput. Math.*, 18(2-4):117–126, 2003.
- [16] R. J. Duffin and A. C. Schaeffer. A class of nonharmonic Fourier series. *Trans. Amer. Math. Soc.*, 72:341–366, 1952.
- [17] Hans G. Feichtinger and K. Gröchenig. Gabor frames and time-frequency analysis of distributions. *J. Funct. Anal.*, 146(2):464–495, 1997.
- [18] Hans G. Feichtinger and Thomas Strohmer, editors. *Gabor analysis and algorithms: Theory and application*. Applied and Numerical Harmonic Analysis. Birkhäuser Boston, Inc., Boston, MA, 1998.
- [19] Hans G. Feichtinger and Thomas Strohmer, editors. *Advances in Gabor analysis*. Applied and Numerical Harmonic Analysis. Birkhäuser Boston, Inc., Boston, MA, 2003.
- [20] Massimo Fornasier and Karlheinz Gröchenig. Intrinsic localization of frames. *Constr. Approx.*, 22(3):395–415, 2005.
- [21] D. Freeman, E. Odell, Th. Schlumprecht, and A. Zsák. Unconditional structures of translates for $L_p(\mathbb{R}^d)$. *Israel J. Math.*, 203(1):189–209, 2014.
- [22] Karlheinz Gröchenig. *Foundations of time-frequency analysis*. Applied and Numerical Harmonic Analysis. Birkhäuser Boston, Inc., Boston, MA, 2001.
- [23] Karlheinz Gröchenig. Localized frames are finite unions of Riesz sequences. *Adv. Comput. Math.*, 18(2-4):149–157, 2003.
- [24] Karlheinz Gröchenig. Localization of frames, Banach frames, and the invertibility of the frame operator. *J. Fourier Anal. Appl.*, 10(2):105–132, 2004.
- [25] Karlheinz Gröchenig. Gabor frames without inequalities. *Int. Math. Res. Not. IMRN*, (23):Art. ID rnm111, 21, 2007.
- [26] Karlheinz Gröchenig. The mystery of Gabor frames. *J. Fourier Anal. Appl.*, 20(4):865–895, 2014.
- [27] Karlheinz Gröchenig, Joaquim Ortega-Cerdà, and José Luis Romero. Deformation of Gabor systems. *Adv. Math.*, 277:388–425, 2015.
- [28] Christopher Heil. History and evolution of the density theorem for Gabor frames. *J. Fourier Anal. Appl.*, 13(2):113–166, 2007.
- [29] Sneha Lata and Vern Paulsen. The Feichtinger conjecture and reproducing kernel Hilbert spaces. *Indiana Univ. Math. J.*, 60(4):1303–1317, 2011.
- [30] Wayne Lawton. The Feichtinger conjecture for exponentials. *J. Nonlinear Anal. Optim.*, 2(1):131–140, 2011.
- [31] K. Mahesh Krishna. Feichtinger conjectures, R_e -conjectures and Weaver’s conjectures for Banach spaces. [arXiv.org/2201.00125v1 \[math.FA\]](https://arxiv.org/2201.00125v1) 1 January, 2022.
- [32] K. Mahesh Krishna and P. Sam Johnson. Dilation theorem for p -approximate Schauder frames for separable Banach spaces. *Palest. J. Math.*, 11(2):384–394, 2022.
- [33] Adam Marcus and Nikhil Srivastava. The solution of the Kadison-Singer problem. In *Current developments in mathematics 2016*, pages 111–143. Int. Press, Somerville, MA, 2018.
- [34] Adam W. Marcus, Daniel A. Spielman, and Nikhil Srivastava. Interlacing families II: Mixed characteristic polynomials and the Kadison-Singer problem. *Ann. of Math. (2)*, 182(1):327–350, 2015.

- [35] Darrin Speegle. Uniform partitions of frames of exponentials into Riesz sequences. *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, 348(2):739–745, 2008.
- [36] Diana T. Stoeva. On a characterization of Riesz bases via biorthogonal sequences. *J. Fourier Anal. Appl.*, 26(4):Paper No. 67, 5, 2020.
- [37] Dan Timotin. The solution of the Kadison-Singer problem. In *Recent advances in operator theory and operator algebras*, pages 117–148. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 2018.
- [38] Nik Weaver. The Kadison-Singer problem in discrepancy theory. *Discrete Math.*, 278(1-3):227–239, 2004.
- [39] Eric Weber. Algebraic aspects of the paving and Feichtinger conjectures. In *Topics in operator theory. Volume 1. Operators, matrices and analytic functions*, volume 202 of *Oper. Theory Adv. Appl.*, pages 569–578. Birkhäuser Verlag, Basel, 2010.